

1 **NOD2 controls expression of genes belonging to the exhaustion program and is located on the**
2 **genome syntenically with TOX3 and CYLD.**

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8 Citations

9 1. Yuan, S.H., Qiu, Z. and Ghosh, A., 2009. TOX3 regulates calcium-dependent transcription in
10 neurons. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 106(8), pp.2909-2914.

11 2. Hrdinka, M., Fiil, B.K., Zucca, M., Leske, D., Bagola, K., Yabal, M., Elliott, P.R., Damgaard, R.B.,
12 Komander, D., Jost, P.J. and Gyrd-Hansen, M., 2016. CYLD limits Lys63-and Met1-linked ubiquitin at
13 receptor complexes to regulate innate immune signaling. Cell reports, 14(12), pp.2846-2858.

14 3. Hnisz, D., Day, D.S. and Young, R.A., 2016. Insulated neighborhoods: structural and functional
15 units of mammalian gene control. Cell, 167(5), pp.1188-1200.